

Terpenoids and Related Compounds. Part IV'. Triterpenoids from the Stem-bark of *Eugenia Jambolana* Lam

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Betulinic acid, friedelin, *epi*-friedelanol, β -sitosterol, and a new ester of *epi*-friedelanol (eugenin) have been isolated from the stem-bark of *Eugenia jambolana* Lam.

Eugenia jambolana Lam, Syn. *Syzygium cumini* Linn., (Fam. Myrtaceae) is a large evergreen tree, found all over India. The bark, seeds, leaves, and fruits of the tree have been used in the indigenous system of medicine. The seeds have been shown to contain ellagic acid¹, essential oil, and oleanolic acid². Recently Nair and Subramanian³ have reported the isolation of three triterpenoids: Eugenia terpenoid A, Eugenia terpenoid B, and acetyloleanolic acid, besides possibly ellagic acid from the yellowish white, fragrant flowers of *E. jambolana*. These workers, however, failed to isolate any triterpenoid from the stem-bark of the tree.

The present communication deals with the chemical investigation of the stem-bark of *E. jambolana*. Benzene extract of the stem-bark was separated into ether-soluble and ether-insoluble fractions. The latter fraction was amorphous and resisted all attempts at crystallisation. The former fraction was separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The acidic material has been shown to be betulinic acid by its conversion to methyl betulinic acid, m.p. 219-20°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 8^\circ$ (CHCl₃), and comparison of its IR spectrum with that of an authentic specimen of methyl betulinic acid.*

The neutral fraction on chromatography over alumina first provided a very small amount of a new substance, m.p. 169-72°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 42^\circ$ (CHCl₃). This substance has been named eugenin (*vide infra*). It was followed by friedelin, m.p. 256-60°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 26^\circ$ (CHCl₃), identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic sample. The third solid to come out of the column was *epi*-friedelanol, m.p. 279-83°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 30^\circ$ (CHCl₃), which was oxidised with chromium trioxide-pyridine complex⁵ to friedelin, m.p. 256-58°, identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic sample. The last crystalline solid from the chromatogram was identified as β -sitosterol.

1. Part III, Sengupta and Khastgir, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 123.
2. Chopra, Nayar, and Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 238.
3. Murti and Rao, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, **20A**, 163.
4. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 457.
5. Poes *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1026.

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Eugenin, the new neutral compound mentioned above, has the molecular formula $C_{38}H_{106}O_{29}$ and shows an IR peak at 1718 cm^{-1} due to an ester carbonyl. The compound was resistant to alkali even under drastic conditions. With sodium methoxide in anhydrous methanol, eugenin did, however, undergo ester exchange and *epi*-friedelanol, identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic specimen, was obtained. This experiment establishes that eugenin is an ester of *epi*-friedelanol ($C_{30}H_{51}OH$) with a fatty acid ($C_{27}H_{53}COOH$). Due to a very poor yield of eugenin, we have so far not been able to identify the fatty acid part. Further, on treatment with lithium aluminium hydride, eugenin furnished *epi*-friedelanol, identified as its acetate.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Extraction of the Bark of E. Jambolana.—Dried and powdered bark (1 kg.) of *E. jambolana* was extracted with benzene for 8 hr. The resinous mass (12 g.) after removal of the benzene was taken in ether and filtered from some amorphous solid which resisted all attempts at crystallisation. The ether solution was shaken with a cold 10% solution of NaOH when a white precipitate appeared in the aqueous layer which was separated and filtered. The ether solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to furnish a partially crystalline material (6 g.).

Betulinic Acid.—The above solid sodium salt was suspended in water and after addition of HCl (conc.) was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to yield a crystalline solid (1.7 g.), m.p. $225-60^\circ$, which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and acetone furnished betulinic acid (1.1 g.), m.p. $306-310^\circ$.

Methyl Betulinate.—An ethereal solution of the preceding acid (1 g.) was esterified with ethereal solution of diazomethane (from 1 g. of nitrosomethylurea) and after usual working up, the crude methyl betulinate was chromatographed over alumina (10 g., deactivated with 0.3 ml of 10% aqueous acetic acid). Elution with petroleum-benzene mixture (3:2) furnished a solid (0.5 g.), m.p. $203-209^\circ$, which on crystallisation from acetone furnished pure methyl betulinate, m.p. $219-20^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D +8^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), identical (IR) with an authentic sample of methyl betulinate of Djerassi. (Found: C, 79.31; H, 10.72. Calc. for $C_{51}H_{50}O_3$: C, 79.10; H, 10.71%).

Investigation of the Partially Crystalline Neutral Material, Eugenin.—The above partially crystalline neutral material (6 g.) was chromatographed over activated alumina (120 g.). After a forerun of a gummy material (1.3 g.), elution with a mixture of petroleum and benzene (4:1) furnished a partially crystalline material (0.2 g.), which on several crystallisations from a mixture of benzene and methanol yielded colorless crystals of eugenin (0.02 g.), m.p. $169-72^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D -42^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). It did not show any colour with tetranitromethane. [Found: C, 83.53; H, 12.74. M.W. (Rast), 788. $C_{38}H_{106}O_2$ requires C, 83.45; H, 12.71%; M.W., 834]. IR peak at 1718 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl).

Friedelin.—Elution with a mixture of petroleum and benzene (3:2) in the above chromatogram furnished a solid (0.8 g.), m.p. $240-46^\circ$, which on crystallisation from a mix-

*All melting points are uncorrected. The petroleum used throughout the investigation had b.p. $60-80^\circ$.

ture of chloroform and methanol afforded a solid, m.p. 256-60°, $[\alpha]_D -26^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It showed negative test with tetranitromethane and an IR peak at 1710 cm^{-1} (six-membered ring ketone). Finally it was identified as friedelin by comparison (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic specimen⁶. (Found: C, 84.25; H, 11.72. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%.)

Friedelin Oxime.—Friedelin was converted into its oxime according to the procedure of Drake and Shrader⁷. The oxime, m.p. 290-94°, did not depress the m.p. of an authentic specimen of friedelin oxime⁶.

epi-Friedelanol.—Elution with a mixture of benzene and ether (4:1) in the above chromatogram furnished a crude solid (0.6 g.), m.p. 270-74°, which on repeated crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol provided pure *epi*-friedelanol, m.p. 279-83°, $[\alpha]_D +30^\circ$ (CHCl_3) (lit.⁸ m.p. 279-83°, $[\alpha]_D +24^\circ$).

epi-Friedelanyl Acetate.—*epi*-Friedelanol (0.2 g.) was acetylated in the usual manner with acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (5 ml). The crude acetate on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished *epi*-friedelanyl acetate, m.p. 290-94°, $[\alpha]_D +38^\circ$ (CHCl_3) (lit.⁸ m.p. 290-94°, $[\alpha]_D +45^\circ$). (Found: C, 81.53; H, 11.36. Calc. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.64; H, 11.56%.)

epi-Friedelanyl Benzoate.—*epi*-Friedelanol (0.13 g.) was benzoylated in the usual manner with benzoyl chloride (2 ml) and pyridine (10 ml). The crude benzoate on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished *epi*-friedelanyl benzoate, m.p. 250-54°, $[\alpha]_D +44^\circ$ (CHCl_3) (lit.⁸ m.p. 254-57°, $[\alpha]_D +40^\circ$).

Friedelin from epi-Friedelanol.—A cold solution of *epi*-friedelanol (0.15 g.) in pyridine (4 ml) was added to a complex, prepared, from chromium trioxide (0.15 g.) in pyridine (1.5 ml), and cooled to 15°. After usual working up, the crude solid, m.p. 252-56°, on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol, furnished friedelin, m.p. 256-58°, identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic specimen of friedelin.

β -Sitosterol.—Elution with a mixture of benzene and ether (1:4) in the above chromatogram furnished a solid (0.6 g.), m.p. 124-30°, which on several crystallisations from a mixture of chloroform and methanol yielded β -sitosterol, m.p. 134-36°, $[\alpha]_D -38^\circ$ (CHCl_3). (Found: C, 84.05; H, 12.40. Calc. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 83.99; H, 12.15%.)

β -Sitosterol Acetate.— β -Sitosterol (0.43 g.) was acetylated in the usual manner with acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (5 ml). The crude acetate on crystallisation from acetone furnished β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 124-26°, $[\alpha]_D -39^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate. (Found: C, 81.67; H, 11.30. Calc. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%.)

Attempted Hydrolysis of Eugenin.—(a). Eugenin (0.09 g.) was refluxed for 30 hr. with KOH (0.5 g.), methanol (25 ml), and benzene (10 ml). After working up as usual, unchanged eugenin (0.08 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 169-70°, was obtained.

6. Sengupta and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 247.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1854.

8. Jefferies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 473.

(b). Eugenin (0.06 g.) was refluxed for 8 hr. with KOH (0.4 g.), water (0.1 ml), and tetrahydrofuran (5 ml). After working up as usual, unchanged eugenin (0.05 g), m.p. and mixed m.p. 168-70°, was obtained.

(c). Eugenin (0.07 g.) was refluxed for 5 hr. with KOH (1 g.) in ethylene glycol (10 ml). After working up as usual, unchanged eugenin (0.06 g), m.p. and mixed m.p. 167-70°, was recovered.

Methanolysis of Eugenin.—Eugenin (0.068 g.) was refluxed for 5 hr. with a solution of sodium methoxide (from 0.5 g. Na and 5ml of methanol) in benzene (7 ml). The reaction mixture was treated with cold water and the neutral material was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to furnish a crystalline solid (0.03 g.), m.p. 250-65°. It was chromatographed over alumina (10 g.) and the solid eluted with benzene on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol afforded *epi*-friedelanol, m.p. 271-75°, identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic specimen.

The above aqueous alkaline layer on acidification provided only a trace of a gummy material which could not be examined further.

Treatment of Eugenin with LiAlH_4 .—A solution of eugenin (0.05 g.) in THF (5 ml) was added to a suspension of LiAlH_4 (0.05 g.) in THF (5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. After working up as usual, a crystalline material, m.p. 226-252°, was obtained. The solid after chromatography on alumina, followed by crystallisation from chloroform-methanol, as above, furnished *epi*-friedelanol, m.p. 270-74°, identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic specimen.

A small fraction of this *epi*-friedelanol was acetylated as usual and the acetate, m.p. 286-90°, was identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with authentic *epi*-friedelanyl acetate.

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